

MAXIMUM MANUFACTURING SECTOR OUTPUT REQUIRED FOR POVERTY REDUCTION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the maximum manufacturing sector output required for poverty reduction in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022. The objectives of the study were to analyze the impact of manufacturing output on poverty reduction, determine the required maximum manufacturing output to reduce poverty and trace the direction of causality between manufacturing output and poverty reduction in Nigeria. Pre-estimation tests of unit root and co-integration were carried out using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests of stationarity and co-integration in order to find out the possibility of mean reversibility and the existence of long run relationship among the variables used in the model. The study employed a quadratic non-linear model to determine the maximum manufacturing sector output required to minimize poverty in Nigeria. The study further applied Error Correction Model (ECM) to trace the speed of adjustment in addition to short run dynamic effects. Granger Causality test was done to trace the direction of causality between variables in the model. The result of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test showed that all the variables were stationary at first difference, I (1) except external debt which was integrated of order two I (2). The result of the non-linear quadratic regression indicated a maximum of 7.65% of the manufacturing output in a long run and 5.378% in a short run to minimize poverty in Nigeria. The result of the short run dynamics indicated that MSO had positive impact on household consumption (proxy for Poverty). A unit increase in manufacturing sector output increased household consumption by 217.43. The findings of the Pairwise Granger Causality test showed a unidirectional causality running from poverty to manufacturing sector output and a bi-directional causality between exchange rate and manufacturing sector output in Nigeria.

Keywords: Manufacturing, Poverty, Output, Causality, Non-linear.

JEL Classification: M2; O4.

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian economy was majorly agrarian before the independence era with agriculture having more 90% of her external source of income. The country's main source of income was derived from exports of primary agricultural products to developed countries.

The commercial activities that were described as industrial activities were carried out by the multinational companies owned by foreigners that had no interest in using the available resources to minimize absolute poverty in Nigeria. These companies were engaged in trade and commerce especially in the area of importation and distribution of manufactured goods and exportation of raw materials to foreign companies for processing. (Banjoko, 2009).

Poverty cycle is a chronic disease in Nigeria in spite of the country's rich mineral endowments. Staggering poverty in the midst of abundant natural resources in Nigeria becomes one of the unsolved problems that seek a solution.

Poverty has multi-dimensional phenomenon which can be seen in the area of deficiency of material income, inadequate access to good standard of living; unemployment, dependency on imports, inflation, hunger and under-nutrition; illness; limited education and fundamental services; persistent rise in mortality and morbidity due to sickness; homelessness and insufficient housing; insecure environments and social exclusion and discrimination.

Poverty is a calamity because the impoverished also face exclusion from social and cultural decision-making processes and overall societal participation. (Ijaiya et al., 2011, Ogbeide, Nwamaka and Agu, 2015).

The Nigeria's manufacturing output ratio to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) measured in billions of US dollars from 2014 to 2022 was gradually increasing in a decreasing rate. The difference between one fiscal year and another was too infinitesimal to create reasonable impact on poverty reduction and sustainable economic performance. The situation is demonstrated with the aid of table 1.1

Table 1.1: Nigeria's Manufacturing Output

Nigeria Manufacturing Output		
Year	Billions of US \$	% of GDP
2022	64.25	13.59%
2021	64.41	14.61%
2020	54.75	12.67%
2019	54.68	11.52%

Source: World Bank (2023)

The percentage contribution of the manufacturing sector output was increasing as its output was increasing except in 2022 where it declined from 14.61% to 13.59%. Persistent issues such as infrastructure deficiencies, power shortages, numerous taxes, and the inflow of imported goods continue to impede the sector's growth. Despite the rapid economic expansion of the nation, a substantial proportion of the populace remains entrenched in poverty. In terms of expansion, Nigeria's gross domestic product (GDP) saw a growth of 69.7 percent from 1992 to 2009, followed by a 27.21 percent increase from 2009 to 2016. Conversely, the poverty gap ratio experienced a decline from 31.1 percent to 21.8 percent between 1992 and 2009 (World Bank, 2017).

The continuous increase in poverty rate in Nigeria despite policy measures to enhance per capita consumption has created doubts on the possibility of reducing poverty in Nigeria to a minimum poverty line. In 2004, the poverty incidence was 64.2 percent of the population, indicating that over 85 million individuals fell below the poverty line using the per capita method. Similarly, the proportion of the population below the poverty line in 2010 was 62.6 percent, encompassing over 95 million people in this category (World Development Report, 2004).

Based on the above discussion, the following questions were addressed in this paper.

- (i) What is the impact of manufacturing sector output on poverty reduction in Nigeria?
- (ii) What is the required maximum manufacturing sector output to reduce poverty in Nigeria?
- (iii) What is the direction of causality between manufacturing output and poverty reduction in Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

The specific objectives of this paper were:

- (i) To analyze the impact of manufacturing sector output on poverty reduction in Nigeria.
- (ii) To determine the required maximum manufacturing output to reduce poverty in Nigeria .
- (iii) To trace the direction of causality between manufacturing output sector and poverty reduction in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Keynesian theory suggests that growth can promote economic development and relieve poverty in its attempt to justify government intervention at the macroeconomic level. The intervention of government includes the provision of capital and public goods, otherwise referred to as socioeconomic expenditure of government (Sachs, 2005). The endogenous growth theory, as developed by Arrow, Romer and Lucas, explains the long-run growth rate of the economy on the bases of endogenous factors against the exogenous factors of the neoclassical growth theory. The theory focuses on positive externalities and spillover effects of knowledge based which will lead to economic development. Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz developed the human capital theory in the 1950s and early 1960s. The theory suggests that individuals and societies derive economic benefits from investments in education. Higher levels of education lead to higher productivity and earnings. Socioeconomic variables are key determinants of health because increased income improves individuals' access to healthier food and drinks, healthier living environments, and healthcare (Biggs, King, Basu and Stuckler (2010).

Agril et al (2020) examined industrial sector performance and poverty reduction in Nigeria using Granger causality test and Ordinary Least Square (OLS). The estimated results revealed that aggregate industrial output (INDQ) had positive impact on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study recommended the need for government to put in place the needed mechanism to ensure that budget allocation to industrial sector is increased

Ehinomen and Adeleke (2012) studied investments in the manufacturing sector with the intent to reduce poverty situation in Nigeria using secondary data. The findings showed that increased investment led to increased manufacturing output.

Simbo, Iwuji and Bagshaw (2012) examined the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector since independence in 1960 using percentage contribution to the Gross Domestic

Product, index of manufactured products, percentage growth rate, manufacturing value added, employment growth rate, and percentage of capacity utilization within this period. Findings of the study showed that the Nigerian manufacturing sector had grossly underperformed in relation to its potentials. Challenges facing the sector were identified as unfavourable business environment, erratic power supply, poor and decaying physical infrastructures, multiple taxations, obsolete technology, high interest rates and inconsistency in government policies.

Sigah (2024) examined the link between real sector development and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The objective of the paper was to examine the impact of real sector variables on poverty rate in Nigeria. The datasets were analyzed using error correction model (ECM) and post-estimation tests. The result of the ECM found that agriculture value added to GDP significantly reduced poverty headcount.

Loayza and Raddatz (2010) examined the cross-country heterogeneity of the poverty response to changes in economic growth by focusing on the structure of output growth. It used a two-sector theoretical model that clarifies the mechanism through which the sectoral composition of growth and associated labour intensity could affect workers' wages. The paper evaluated differential poverty-reducing impact of sectoral growth at various levels of disaggregation, and the role of unskilled labor intensity in such differential impact. The result of the paper stated that the size of economic growth and its composition matters accounted for poverty with the largest contributions from unskilled labour-intensive sectors (agriculture, construction, and manufacturing).

Agri, et al. (2020) examined industrial sector performance and poverty reduction in Nigeria using and time series data sourced from different sources spanning from 1981-2018. Econometric techniques of stationary unit test (ADF), Johansen Co-integration test and Granger causality test, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and multiple regressions were employed in the paper. The results revealed that aggregate industrial output (INDQ) and industrial employment (INDEM) had positive impact on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The result of the Granger causality test of the paper revealed a unidirectional causality running from aggregate industrial output (INDQ) to poverty rate (POVR), poverty rate (POVR). The study recommends that the government of Nigeria should put in place the needed mechanism to ensure that budget allocation to industrial sector is increased for adequate industrialization.

The model

The theoretical framework of this paper was based on Keynes theory of growth and poverty which suggests that economic growth can promote economic development and thus reduce poverty. The theory took into account the existence of a poverty trap, the economic policy framework, the fiscal framework and fiscal traps, physical geography, governance patterns and failures, cultural barriers and geopolitics. In this regard, poverty in a given country might be heavily affected by the presence of a very weak institutional environment including corruption.

This study employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test to check the order of integration of the variables in the models.

The general form of ADF was specified as:

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_2 \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta Y_{t-i} + U_t \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where: Y = time series variable,

T = a linear time trend,

Δ = the first difference operator,

β_i = constant,

n = the optimum number of lags in the independent variables and

U = random term.

The long run relationship of the variables used in the model was checked by the use of ADF Co-integration test. The ADF co-integration test was specified as:

$$\Delta U_t = \beta_t + \beta_2 t + \partial U_{t-1} + \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta U_{t-i} + e_t \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Where U_t = the residual generated from the long run equation

The model adopted by this paper was the Error Correction Model (ECM) which was first mentioned by Yule (1926) and Granger and Newbold (1974) to address the problem of spurious correlation in time series. Error Correction Model (ECM) belongs to multiple time series models which are used when the underlying variables have a long-run common stochastic trend. The ECM directly estimate the speed at which a dependent variable returns to equilibrium after a change in other variables. The study also adopted Non-Linear Threshold Model using the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) by Kuznets (1955). The model in this case was a quadratic model meant to find the maximum value of manufacturing output required for poverty reduction in Nigeria.

The functional form of the model was specified as:

$$POVR = f(MSO, INF, EXR, TOP, EXD) \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where:

POVR = Poverty Reduction

MSO = Manufacturing Sector Output

INF = Inflation Rate

EXR = Exchange Rate

TOP = Trade Openness

EXD = External Debt

Equation 2 was transformed into econometric form in order to trace the impact of each explanatory variable on poverty in addition to capturing the random walk inherent in the model as shown in equation 4.

The structural form of the model was specified as:

$$POVR_t = a_0 + a_1MSO_t + a_3INF_t + a_4EXR_t + a_6TOP_t + a_7EXD_t + u_{it} \dots \dots \dots 4$$

where all the variables remained as defined

Equation 4 was transformed to Error Correction Model in order to capture the speed of adjustment and short run dynamic of the variables as shown in equation 5

$$\Delta POVR_{t-i} = a_0 + a_1\Delta MSO_{t-i} + a_3\Delta INF_{t-i} + a_4\Delta EXR_{t-i} + a_6\Delta TOP_{t-i} + a_7\Delta EXD_{t-i} + a_8ECM_t u_{it} \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where:

all the variables remain as defined

$\Delta =$ differenced operator

$a_8 =$ Error Correction Parameter for measuring speed of adjustment

$\mu_t =$ Error term

Objective two is to ascertain the optimal manufacturing output required to reduce poverty in Nigeria. The functional form of the model will be specified as:

$$POVR_t = MSO, MSO^2, INF, EXR, GXP, TOP, EXD) \dots \dots \dots 6$$

Where: All the variables remain as defined

The basic equation to be estimated was specified as:

$$POVR_t = a_0 + a_1MSO_t + a_2MSO_t^2 + a_3INF_t + a_4EXR_t + a_5GXP_t + a_6TOP_t + a_7EXD_t + u_{it} \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

where MSO and its squared term were the variables of interest.

After estimating equation (7), the optimal manufacturing sector output threshold was estimated using the following mathematical operation:

$$PD^* = -\frac{a_1}{a_2} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

Where: PD* = the optimal manufacturing sector output threshold

$a_1 =$ the coefficient of the manufacturing sector output linear term and

$a_2 =$ the coefficient of the manufacturing sector output quadratic term.

Causality analysis was done using the granger causality test in order to ascertain the direction of causality between variables used in the model. This was specified as:

$$POVR_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_1 POVR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^n B_2 EXD_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 GAE_{t-3} + \sum_{i=4}^n B_4 EXRT_{t-4} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 GXP_{t-5} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 TOP_{t-6} + \mu \dots 9$$

$$EXD_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_1 EXD_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^n B_2 GAE_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 EXRT_{t-4} + \sum_{i=4}^n B_4 TOP_{t-4} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 GXP_{t-5} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 POVR_{t-6} + \mu \dots 10$$

$$GAE_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_1 GAE_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^n B_2 EXD_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 EXRT_{t-3} + \sum_{i=4}^n B_4 TOP_{t-4} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 GXP_{t-5} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 POVR_{t-6} + \mu \dots \dots 11$$

$$EXRT_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_1 EXRT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^n B_2 EXD_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 GAE_{t-3} + \sum_{i=4}^n B_4 TOP_{t-4} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 GXP_{t-5} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 POVR_{t-6} + \mu \dots \dots 12$$

$$GXP_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_1 GXP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^n B_2 EXD_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 GAE_{t-3} + \sum_{i=4}^{i=n} B_4 EXRT_{t-4} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 TOP_{t-5} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 POVR_{t-6} + \mu \dots \dots 13$$

$$TOP_t = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_1 TOP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^n B_2 EXD_{t-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{i=n} B_3 GAE_{t-3} + \sum_{i=4}^{i=n} B_4 EXRT_{t-4} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 GXP_{t-5} + \sum_{i=5}^n B_5 POVR_{t-6} + \mu \dots 14$$

Decision Rule:

If the probability value is less than 0.05, the alternative hypothesis is accepted otherwise the null hypothesis is accepted

Post estimation tests of Normality, serial correlation and Heteroscedasticity were carried out.

the data utilized in this study was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics. It covered a period of 23 years from 1981-2022 based on the availability of data.

RESULTS

The distributive properties of the data used in this work were explained using descriptive statistics as shown with the aid of table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	POVR	MSO	INF	EXR	TOP	EXD
Mean	24648.95	26.54643	17.62400	115.6556	32.42643	2709.434
Median	22469.35	23.25000	12.15500	114.8990	34.02000	669.3252
Maximum	52453.03	64.41000	72.84000	425.9792	53.28000	19004.84
Minimum	8326.311	8.080000	-3.000000	0.617708	9.140000	2.331200
Std. Dev.	13939.94	16.25963	16.88901	118.1074	11.98935	4270.409
Skewness	0.384314	0.766119	1.835560	1.025345	-0.387939	2.375845
Kurtosis	1.641595	2.568822	5.377670	3.230143	2.331728	8.223511
Jarque-Bera	17.05236	17.73567	133.9131	29.80807	7.340030	349.0454
Probability	0.000198	0.000141	0.000000	0.000000	0.025476	0.000000
Sum	4141024.	4459.800	2960.831	19430.15	5447.640	455184.8
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.25E+10	44150.70	47634.86	2329542.	24005.34	3.05E+09
Observations	168	168	168	168	168	168

Source: Author's computation using Eview version 9

Table 1 indicates that the measures of central tendency of the variables used in the work had a narrow range of differences. Poverty reduction (POVR) had a mean of 24648.95 as the highest mean and its media (2246945) was also the highest in the distribution. Other variables such as Manufacturing Sector Output (MSO), Inflation (INF), Exchange Rate (EXR), Trade Openness (TOP) and External Debt (EXD) had a mean of 26.54643, 17.62400, 115.6556, 32.42643 and 2709.434 respectively. This indicated that the center of the distribution varied as we move from one variable to another.

The maximum value of POVOR was 52453.03 while its minimum value was 8326.311. This showed a difference of 44,126.719 within the period covered by the study. The maximum values for INF, EXR, TOP and EXD were 64.41000, 72.84000, 425.9792, 53.28000 and 19004.84 respectively. The minimum values of these variables were very low except poverty thereby indicating high values of their ranges.

The standard deviations of MSO, INF and TOP showed evidence of no much difference between the center of each information and observations. There were much differences among the standard deviation of POVOR, EXR and EXD as their values were 13939.94, 118.1074 and 4270.409 respectively. This showed that the standard deviations differed much from their mean values and among them.

The condition for normal distribution states that the skewness value should be between 0 and 1 and the kurtosis value to be within the range of -3 and 3. This condition was fulfilled except inflation rate, exchange rate and external debt which had Kurtosis of 5.37767, 3.23 and 8.2235 respectively. The probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistics for each variable was less than the 5% critical value and this indicated that the variables were normally distributed.

The ADF unit root test was carried out in order to find out the properties of the variables and the result was summarized in table 2

Table 2: Result of Unit root test

Variables	Level form		First Diff		Second Diff		Order of integration
	ADF Stat.	ADF critical	ADF Stat.	ADF critical	ADF Stat.	ADF critical	
POVR	0.0487	-2.879	-8.7297	-2.879	===	-2.879	I(1)
MSO	-0.503	-2.879	-12.84	-2.879	===	-2.879	I(1)
INF	-2.7252	-2.879	-12.807	-2.879	===	-2.879	I(1)
EXR	1.477931	-2.879	-4.1483	-2.879	===	-2.879	I(1)
TOP	-2.3199	-2.879	-12.826	-2.879	===	-2.879	I(1)
EXD	1.179452	-2.879	-1.9074	-2.879	-31.546	-2.879	I(2)

Source: *Author's Computation Using E-views 10.*

Table 2 clearly showed that all the variables were stationary at first difference except external debt which was integrated of order two I (2). The ADF calculated was compared with the ADF critical value of 5% level. The ADF calculated in level form for POVR was 0.0487 which was less than the ADF critical value of 2.879. In this case POVR became stationary when it was differenced once as its ADF became -8.7297. External debt was differenced twice before its ADF became absolutely greater than its 5% critical value. In this study external debt was integrated of order two, I (2).

The result of the ADF cointegration test was shown in table 3.

Table 3: ADF Co-Integration Test

Null Hypothesis: ECM has a unit root		
Exogenous: Constant		
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=13)		
	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.358393	0.0139
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.469691
	5% level	-2.878723
	10% level	-2.576010
*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.		

Source: *Author's Computation*

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller cointegration test statistic (ECM) was -3.358393 which was absolutely greater than 5% test critical value of -2.95. This showed that the variables were cointegrated thereby having a long run relationship.

The result of the long run regression was presented in table 4 in order to ascertain the long run effect of manufacturing sector output on poverty.

Table 4: Long run regression result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	6320.355	953.2532	6.630300	0.0000
MSO	178.7647	23.98802	7.452249	0.0000
INF	-10.72810	16.88053	-0.635531	0.5260
EXR	146.4119	5.387760	27.17492	0.0000
TOP	56.45794	23.45619	2.406953	0.0172
EXD	-1.842449	0.128763	-14.30885	0.0000

The result of the long run regression showed that the constant was 6320.355 when all the explanatory variables were assumed statistically equal to zero. The result indicated that poverty had positive relationship with manufacturing Sector Output (MSO), exchange rate (EXR), and Trade Openness (TOP) in a long run. It was observed from the result that poverty had negative relationship with Inflation Rate (INF) and External Debt (EXD). The result further showed that an increase in manufacturing output significantly increased poverty by 178.765. A unit increase in exchange rate and trade openness also increased poverty significantly by 146.4119 and 56.4579 respectively. The result also indicated that an increase in inflation decreased poverty by 10.728 but not significant while an increase in external debt significantly reduced poverty by 1.843.

Error Correction Model (ECM) was carried out in order to estimate the speed of adjustment and the short run dynamic within the time frame of the investigation. The result of the ECM was presented in table 5

Table 5: Error Correction Model (ECM) result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	44.48624	123.7559	0.359468	0.7197
D(MSO)	217.4302	42.25399	5.145791	0.0000
D(INF)	-8.953901	16.90642	-0.529616	0.5971
D(EXR)	72.52805	20.54604	3.530025	0.0005
D(TOP)	-43.47027	29.54089	-1.471529	0.1431
D(EXD)	-0.316049	0.317216	-0.996323	0.3206
ECM	-0.107120	0.035598	3.009196	0.0030

Source: Author's computation using Eview

The sign of the speed of adjustment was -0,107 with a t-statistics of 3.009 and p-value of 0.003. This showed that the residual had up to 10.7% chance of coming back to equilibrium within the short run. The result indicated that MSO and EXR positively influenced Poverty reduction by 217.43 and 72.528 respectively.

The result of the maximum manufacturing output required to minimize poverty in Nigeria using quadratic pattern of the model was presented in table 6.

Table 6: The result of the maximum MSO for poverty reduction

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	11166.63	1290.109	8.655576	0.0000
MSO	-274.6978	90.56339	-3.033211	0.0028
MSO ²	7.652663	1.481355	5.165990	0.0000
INF	-8.620509	15.68819	-0.549490	0.5834
EXR	158.0970	5.492846	28.78234	0.0000
TOP	61.36130	21.81268	2.813102	0.0055
EXD	-2.492073	0.173562	-14.35839	0.0000

Source: Author's computation

$$\text{maximum MSO} = \frac{274.6979}{7.653663} = 35.89\%$$

The result of the estimation showed that a maximum of 35.89% of the manufacturing output was required to minimize poverty in Nigeria. The t-statistics and the p-value of 5.166 and 0.000 showed that the maximum output played a significant role in poverty reduction within a long run. The result further showed that all the variables except inflation rate were significantly affecting poverty.

In a short run, the result of the required maximum output of the manufacturing output capable of reducing poverty in Nigeria was presented in table 7.

Table 7: Maximum manufacturing output for poverty reduction in a short run

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	33.20740	118.8246	0.279466	0.7803
D(MSO)	-114.0034	95.58658	-1.192671	0.2348
D(MSO ²)	5.378270	1.404562	3.829145	0.0002
D(INF)	-3.464484	16.29096	-0.212663	0.8319
D(EXR)	80.58238	19.83315	4.063015	0.0001
D(TOP)	-51.79556	28.43831	-1.821331	0.0704
D(EXD)	-0.699245	0.320506	-2.181693	0.0306
ECM	0.103639	0.034181	3.032093	0.0028

Source: Author's computation

$$\text{Maximum MSO} = \frac{114.0034}{5,378270} = 21.2\%$$

The result of the short run dynamics showed that 21.2% of manufacturing sector output was required to minimize poverty in a short run in Nigeria. It further indicated that the required output played a significant impact in reshaping poverty as shown by its p-value of 0.0002. The result also showed that manufacturing sector output had no significant effect on poverty in a short run as shown by its p-value of 0.2348.

Causality test was carried out to ascertain the direction of causality relationship between the variables used in the model. The result of the Granger Causality was presented in table 8.

Table 8: Granger Causality Result

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
MSO does not Granger Cause POVR	166	0.09342	0.9109
POVR does not Granger Cause MSO		3.64826	0.0282
INF does not Granger Cause POVR	166	0.07194	0.9306
POVR does not Granger Cause INF		0.34646	0.7077
EXR does not Granger Cause POVR	166	2.52647	0.0831
POVR does not Granger Cause EXR		0.20125	0.8179
EXR does not Granger Cause MSO	166	4.92675	0.0084
MSO does not Granger Cause EXR		3.22913	0.0422

The result of the Pairwise Granger Causality tests showed a unidirectional causality running from poverty to manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. The result also showed a bi-directional causality between exchange rate and manufacturing sector output. There was no causality between inflation and poverty, and exchange rate and poverty.

The hypotheses of the study were tested based on the 5% level of confidence as shown.

H₀₁: Manufacturing output has no significant impact on poverty reduction in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept Ho if t_i is less than 5% critical value

The result of the long run regression showed that manufacturing sector output had significant positive impact in poverty reduction in Nigeria. The t-statistics was 0.000 signifying a significant impact of the manufacturing sector output in poverty reduction in Nigeria. The result of the short run dynamic also confirmed the significant impact of the manufacturing sector output on poverty reduction by its p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and a conclusion was made that manufacturing sector output had a significant impact on poverty reduction in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no required maximum manufacturing output to reduce poverty in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept Ho if t_i is less than 5% critical value

The result of the estimation confirmed that a maximum of 35.89% of the manufacturing output was required to minimize poverty in a long run in Nigeria. This was shown by its t-statistics and the p-value of 5.166 and 0.000. It was also confirmed by the result of the short run that 21.2% was required for this purpose. The result was an indication that the maximum output required played a significant role in poverty reduction in Nigeria. Based on this the null hypothesis was also rejected and the alternative was chosen.

H₀₃: There is no direction of causality between manufacturing output and poverty reduction in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Accept Ho if t_i is less than 5% critical value

The result of the Pairwise Granger Causality tests confirmed a unidirectional causality running from poverty to manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. It was also confirmed by the result that bi-directional causality between exchange rate and manufacturing sector output existed within

the period. Based on this, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative that directional causality exists between manufacturing output and poverty reduction in Nigeria was accepted

CONCLUSION

The result of the long run and short run regression showed that manufacturing sector output had significant positive impact in poverty reduction in Nigeria as indicated by their p-values of 0.000 each. It was concluded from the result of the non-linear quadratic regression that a maximum of 7.65% of the manufacturing sector output was required to minimize poverty in a long run in Nigeria. There was also evidence of a unidirectional causality running from poverty to manufacturing sector output and a bi-directional causality between exchange rate and manufacturing sector output within the period under investigation

Therefore, this paper recommends that up to 5% increase in annual plan for Small and Medium scale manufacturing enterprises should be aided by the government and up to 7.65% of the manufacturing activities should be subsidized to reduce poverty in Nigeria.

References

- 1) Aderounmu, B., Azuh, D., Onanuga, O., Oluwatomisin, O., Ebenezer, B., Azuh, A., & Amoo, E. O. (2021). Poverty drivers and Nigeria's development: Implications for policy intervention. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2021.1927495>
- 2) Agri1, M, Gonya, T.J., Eneji A.I, Habila, H, & Uzochukwu P. C. (2020) Industrial Sector Performance and Poverty Reduction in Nigeria: 1981-2018 Eneji . *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)* Volume 8, Issue 12, December 2020, PP 64-79 www.arcjournals.org
- 3) Alkire S, & Robles G (2017). Multidimensional Poverty Index – 2017: Brief methodological note and results. Oxford Poverty Hum Dev Initiat. <https://ophi.org.uk/multidimensionalpoverty-index-summer-2017-briefmethodological-note-and-results/>
- 4) Amjad, R & Kemal A.R. (1997) Macroeconomic Policies and their Impact on Poverty Alleviation in Pakistan. *The Pakistan Development Review*, Vol. 36, No. 1 (Spring 1997), pp. 39-68
- 5) Banjoko, S. A. (2009). *The Nigerian Manufacturing Sector: Bumpy Past and Shaky Future what Options for survival?* University of Lagos Inaugural Lecture series.
- 6) Biggs B, King L, Basu S, & Stuckler D (2010). Is wealthier always healthier? The impact of national income level, inequality, and poverty on public health in Latin America. *Soc Sci Med*, 71 (2):266–27
- 7) Central Bank of Nigeria (2022). *Statistical Bulletin*, 20. Abuja; Research Department. Central Bank of Nigeria.
- 8) Deutsch J, & Silber J (2005). Measuring multidimensional poverty: An empirical comparison of various approaches. *Rev Income Wealth*, 51 (1):145–174.
- 9) Ehinomen C. & Adeleke A, (2012) Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria Through Investments in the Manufacturing Sector. *Ehinomen*, Vol 6, No 4 (2012)
- 10) Evans School Policy Analysis and Research EPAR#327. (2016). *Economic Growth and Poverty in Nigeria*.
- 11) Harnisch, M. (2015). *Industry 4.0: The future of productivity and growth in manufacturing industries*. Boston consulting group, 9(1), 54-89.

- 12) Ijaiya, G. T., Bello, R. A., Ajayi, M. A., Ijaiya, M. A., & Adeyemi, S. L. (2011).). Economic Growth And Poverty Reduction In Nigeria. International Journal of Business and social Science. *Journal of Economic Development*, 36(3), 45-57.
- 13) Loayza, N. V. & Raddatz, C. (2010) The composition of growth matters for poverty alleviation. *Journal of Development Economics* , Volume 93, Issue 1, Pages 137-151
- 14) Nozaki K, Oshio T (2016). Multidimensional poverty and perceived happiness: Evidence from China. *Asian Economic Journal*, 30 (3):275–293. 20.
- 15) Ogbeide, O., Nwamaka, E. & Agu, D. (2005). *Asians Economic and Financial Review: Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria*.
- 16) Reid C (2016). *The wounds of exclusion poverty, women’s health, and social justice*. New York: Routledge.
- 17) Sigah, L. E. (2024) Real Sector Development and Poverty Reduction in Nigeria *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 2024 issue viii volume viii
- 18) Simbo A. Banjoko., Iwuji, I. I. & Bagshaw, K. (2012). The Performance of the Nigerian Manufacturing Sector: A 52-Year Analysis of Growth and Retrogression (1960-2012). *Journal of Asian Business Strategy*, 2(8), 177 -191.
- 19) World Bank (2017). *World Development Indicators*. <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>
- 20) *World Development Report 2004: Making Services Work for Poor People*. World Bank and Oxford University Press.